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ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF TOBACCO SMOKING ON THE HEALTH
OF ADOLESCENTS

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Annotation: Over the past decade, there has been not only a quantitative increase in the prevalence of tobacco smoking among adolescents, but also a qualitative change — an increase in the proportion of adolescents with an established addiction to smoking. It is obvious that preventive programs for the formation of stable stereotypes of a healthy lifestyle should begin in earlier age groups. Solving the urgent task of reducing the prevalence of bad habits among adolescents requires interdepartmental cooperation, combining the efforts of not only doctors, teachers, parents, social workers, but also the whole society.

Keywords: bronchial asthma, quantitative increase, development of diseases

In a number of works on the role of the family in the development of behavioral disorders in adolescents, factors contributing to the use of cigarettes are noted. It has been established that the family has a great influence on the formation of addiction to smoking: smoking of parents increases the risk of developing a bad habit in children by 1.5 times, and smoking of brothers and sisters by 2.5 times.

Domestic and foreign studies provide quite a lot of facts on the prevalence of tobacco smoking among both adults and children, however, for an objective assessment, we need our own additional studies that would reflect the dynamics of the process, and this can be achieved only during continuous monitoring of the prevalence of tobacco smoking among children and adolescents. Smoking harms not only those who smoke, but also those who are nearby. Passive smoking leads to hyperactivity of the child's bronchi, which serves as a prerequisite for the development of diseases occurring with bronchial obstruction syndrome (obstructive bronchitis, bronchial asthma, bronchiolitis). It has been established that children exposed to tobacco smoke suffer from respiratory diseases more often and more severely, and have a higher risk of developing otitis media. A close relationship has been established between air pollution by tobacco smoke from smoking parents and the development of chronic cough in children.

Thus, it can be stated that there is a proven and statistically justified link between passive smoking and the occurrence of diseases such as bronchial asthma, bronchiolitis, food allergy, SIDS, otitis media. Children affected by the surrounding tobacco smoke are more likely to see a doctor, are hospitalized more often and much more public money is spent on their treatment.

A large number of works are devoted to the study of the influence of tobacco smoke on the health of children and adolescents. Summarizing the experience of studies conducted by various scientists, we can conclude that there are no methods to study the degree of influence of tobacco on the functional state of the body in a state of pre-illness, when there are no obvious clinical manifestations yet. Considering the ethical aspects, noninvasive research methods have an advantage.

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Thus, there is currently a trend towards an increase in the prevalence of tobacco use in the modern adolescent population and a decrease in the age of the smoker. This is an unfavorable prognosis for the health of the younger generation and a risk factor for the development of chronic pathology in children.

Tobacco smoking contributes to the increase in morbidity and mortality from non-communicable diseases (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, cardiovascular diseases), which develop much earlier if tobacco use occurs in adolescence. In order to stop the growth of the spread of tobacco smoking, properly formed preventive programs aimed specifically at school age are needed. To study the effect of tobacco smoking on the respiratory and cardiovascular systems of the body before the development of diseases or chronic lung pathology, informative and preferably non-invasive research methods are needed, and it is also necessary to study markers such as carbon monoxide and nicotine metabolite cotinine.

Programs aimed at studying the impact of tobacco smoking on the health of children and adolescents in a state of pre-illness, as well as preventive measures, will help reduce the incidence rate among children and, consequently, improve their quality of life.

As a result of signing this document, countries should change their legislation on tobacco control within a certain period and create national programs in this direction. In France, the implementation of the national program Paris without Tobacco (PST) showed that among adolescent children there was a decrease in the prevalence of smoking from 44.5% to 36.4%. At the beginning of 2008 to the Framework Convention on Tobacco Control, and a national tobacco control strategy is being developed. According to the study "Global Adult Survey on Tobacco Consumption" (GATS), 60.2% of men and 21.7% of women smoke. Within the framework of the Global Youth Tobacco Survey (GYTS) program, implemented on the initiative of WHO, 14 112 students of grades 8-10 were examined. More than half of the schoolchildren have already tried smoking, and every second of them subsequently became a smoker. Despite strict laws and anti-smoking programs, the problem of tobacco use among children and adolescents remains relevant.

The prevalence of smoking is defined as the proportion (usually expressed as a percentage) of the population that is smokers in a specific period of time and expresses the ratio of the number of smokers in the study population to the total number of the study population, expressed as a percentage.

The analysis of the identification of the fact of smoking by parents and the close environment of the child was carried out according to the data of the parents of the studied children and the comparison of data with the degree of tobacco consumption, gender and age of initiation of smoking.

When assessing the prevalence of smoking among children and adolescents, the questionnaire method is important. According to our research, it was revealed that as a result of "direct" questioning, the prevalence was 23.3%, and with anonymous questioning - 35.1%.

An analysis of the fact of smoking by parents and the child's close environment showed that the degree of tobacco consumption by a child directly depends on the presence of smoking relatives, so it was revealed that in 36.2% of "heavy smokers" the mother

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smokes, in 63.3% the father smokes and in 27.2% both parents smoke. Among smokers, "occasionally" it is also observed that in 36.3% the mother smokes, but already the use of tobacco products by the father is observed in 45.4% of cases, and both parents - in 18.1%. In contrast, children who do not use tobacco products at the time of the survey, that is, who are "former smokers", have a lower percentage of smoking parents: mother - 24.1%, father - 47.5% and both parents - 17.5%. Smoking by parents is a prerequisite for starting a child's smoking, and in turn, an increase in smoking family members increases the degree of tobacco consumption in children.

When correlating the degree of tobacco consumption and smoking of friends of children and adolescents, it was revealed that in 90% of cases, both "heavy smokers" and children "smoking occasionally" smoke friends, while "former smokers" use of tobacco products among children occurs in 68%.

Thus, the study showed that out of 756 children and adolescents surveyed, almost one in three uses tobacco products. Initiation to smoking most often occurs at primary school age, and by adolescence, dependence on smoking is already forming. Thus, 12.6% of respondents ($p=0.017$) are "heavy smokers" and the largest percentage is observed at the age of 15-17 years.

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